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Research Article

**CARDIAC ARREST MANAGEMENT WITH
EXTRACORPOREAL LIFE SUPPORT : SYSTEMATIC
REVIEW IN LITERATURE****Dalal AlAnazi^{1*}, Afnan Basallom², Abrar Najjar², Nura Alanazi³, Naif Alomar⁴, Saud Althunayan⁴, Rawan Mirza², Talal Alsharari⁵, Ali Najmi⁶, Bayan Fatani²,**¹ King Faisal University, Al-Hasa, Saudi Arabia² Umm al-Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia³ Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia⁴ Imam Mohammed Ibn Saud Islamic University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia⁵ Aljouf university, Aljouf, Saudi Arabia⁶ Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia**Abstract**

This review is aiming to systematically summarize and compare the literature on cardiac arrest management with extracorporeal life support. The present review was conducted by searching in Medline, Embase, Web of Science, Science Direct, BMJ journal and Google Scholar for, researches, review articles and reports, published over the past years. Books published on cardiac arrest management with extracorporeal life support. If several studies had similar findings, we randomly selected one or two to avoid repetitive.

This review found In cardiac arrest, the use of ECLS was associated with an increased survival rate as well as an increase in favorable neurological outcome. In the setting of cardiogenic shock there was an increased survival with ECLS.

Keywords: *Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation, Extracorporeal life support, Cardiac arrest, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), also known as extracorporeal life support (ECLS), is an extracorporeal technique of providing prolonged cardiac and respiratory support to persons whose heart and lungs are unable to provide an adequate amount of gas exchange or perfusion to sustain life. The technology for ECMO is largely derived from cardiopulmonary bypass, which provides shorter-term support with arrested native circulation [1].

This intervention has mostly been used on children, but it is seeing more use in adults with cardiac and respiratory failure. ECMO works by removing blood from the person's body and artificially removing the carbon dioxide and oxygenating red blood cells. Generally, it is used either post-cardiopulmonary bypass or in late stage treatment of a person with profound heart and/or lung failure, although it is now seeing use as a treatment for cardiac arrest in certain centers, allowing treatment of the underlying cause of arrest while circulation and oxygenation are supported [2].

METHODS:

The present review was conducted December 2018 in accordance with the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) declaration standards for systematic reviews. We reviewed all the topics on cardiac arrest management with extracorporeal life support. To achieve this goal, we searched Medline, Embase, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Google Scholar for researches, review articles and reports, published over the past 15 years. Books published on extracorporeal life support.

Our search was completed without language restrictions. Then we extracted data on study year, study design, and key outcome on iron deficiency. The selected studies were summarized and unreproducible studies were excluded. Selected data is shown in the Table 1.

Inclusion criteria

Patients with ECLS support during CPR

Exclusion criteria

Patients without ECLS support during CPR

Data extraction and analysis

Information relating to each of the systematic review elements was extracted from the studies and collated in qualitative tables. Direct analysis of the studies of cardiac arrest management with extracorporeal life

support is made with extreme caution, as different sampling techniques can provide bias as overview of the assemblage.

RESULTS:

Between January 2006 and September 2011, 79 patients were supported with either an Impella axial flow pump (n = 7) or a Tandem Heart centrifugal pump (n = 11), or with ECMO (n = 61) therapy for cardiogenic shock in a single institution. Pertinent variables and post procedural events were analyzed in this cohort of patients using a prospectively maintained clinical database. The in-hospital mortality, successful weaning from mechanical circulatory support, bridge to long-term destination support device and heart transplantation, and limb complications did not differ between the 2 groups based on intention-to-treat analysis. Age was the only independent predictor for in-hospital survival. In this cohort of patients, short-term support devices and ECMO achieved comparable results. In the modern era of medical cost restraints, ECMO may be more cost effective for patients with post infarction- or decompensated cardiomyopathy-related cardiogenic shock. Larger randomized trials may be necessary to this topic [7].

The impact of extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation was estimated in matched patients. Intact survival rate was higher in the matched extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation group than in the matched conventional cardiopulmonary resuscitation group (29.2% [7/24] vs. 8.3% [2/24], log-rank $p = 0.018$). According to the predictor analysis, only pupil diameter on hospital arrival was associated with neurologic outcome (adjusted hazard ratio, 1.39 per 1-mm increase; 95% confidence interval, 1.09-1.78; $p = 0.008$) [8].

Of 499 patients suitable for inclusion, 444 and 55 patients were enrolled in the CCPR and ECPR group, respectively. The predicted duration for a favorable neurologic outcome (CPC1, 2) is <21 minutes of CPR in only CCPR patients. The matched ECPR group with ≥ 21 minutes of CPR duration had a more favorable neurological outcome than the matched CCPR group at 3 months post-arrest. In matched ECPR group, younger age, witnessed arrest without initial asystole rhythm, early achievement of mean arterial pressure ≥ 60 mmHg, low rate of ECPR-related complications, and therapeutic hypothermia were significant factors for expecting good neurologic outcome [4].

Table (1) Results from Sequencing Studies.

Authors	Study design	Setting	Sample	Result
Chou et al. 2010.³	Retrospective	Taiwan	66 patient	The survival rate was 34.9% for patients who received ECPR and 21.8% for those who received conventional CPR (p=0.4). Increased survival rates to hospital discharge were seen in patients with ST segment elevation (p<0.01), or had initial rhythm of ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation (VT/VF) during resuscitation (p=0.031).
Kim et al.2013.⁴	Prospective	Korea	499 patient	Of 499 patients suitable for inclusion, 444 and 55 patients were enrolled in the CCPR and ECPR group, respectively. The predicted duration for a favorable neurologic outcome (CPC1, 2) is < 21 minutes of CPR in only CCPR patients. The matched ECPR group with ≥ 21 minutes of CPR duration had a more favorable neurological outcome than the matched CCPR group at 3 months post-arrest. In matched ECPR group, younger age, witnessed arrest without initial asystole rhythm, early achievement of mean arterial pressure ≥ 60 mmHg, low rate of ECPR-related complications, and therapeutic hypothermia were significant factors for expecting good neurologic outcome.
Sakamoto et al. 2011.⁵	Prospective	Japan	454 patient	In OHCA patients with VF/VT on the initial ECG, a treatment bundle including ECPR, therapeutic hypothermia and IABP was associated with improved neurological outcome at 1 and 6 months after OHCA.
Sattler et al. 2013.⁶	Retrospective	Germany	24 patient	in one patient, ECLS was placed before PCI, in nine patients immediately after PCI and in two patients ECLS therapy was initiated within 24–48 h after PCI with IABP support. Peripheral vessel complications and blood transfusions are shown in the supplementary data. Only one study reported the incidence of renal failure, with renal failure occurring in 58.3 % of patients treated with ECLS and in 25.0 % of the control patients
Chamogeorgakis et al.2011.⁷	Retrospective	USA	79 patient	79 patients were supported with either an Impella axial flow pump (n = 7) or a Tandem Heart centrifugal pump (n = 11), or with ECMO (n = 61) therapy for cardiogenic shock in a single institution. Pertinent variables and post procedural events were analyzed in this cohort of patients using a prospectively maintained clinical database. The in-hospital mortality, successful weaning from mechanical circulatory support, bridge to long-term destination support device and heart transplantation, and limb complications did not differ between the 2 groups based on intention-to-treat analysis
Maekawa et al.2004.⁸	Prospective	Japan	165 patient	Extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation can improve neurologic outcome after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest of cardiac origin; furthermore, pupil diameter on hospital arrival may be a key predictor to identify extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation candidates.

DISCUSSION:

Veno-arterial extracorporeal life support (ECLS) is increasingly used in patients during cardiac arrest and, to support both cardiac and pulmonary function.

We performed a systematic review and of cohort studies comparing mortality in patients treated with and without ECLS support in the setting of refractory cardiac arrest complicating acute myocardial infarction.

This is comprehensive and rigorous systematic review was showed that the percentage of patients who were successfully weaned from ECLS and the percentage of patients who were bridged to long-term ventricular assist device or heart transplant are shown in the supplementary data. Only Sattler et al. reported the time of device placement: in one patient, ECLS was placed before PCI, in nine patients immediately after PCI and in two patients ECLS therapy was initiated within 24–48 h after PCI with IABP support. Peripheral vessel complications and blood transfusions are shown in the supplementary data. Only one study reported the incidence of renal failure, with renal failure occurring in 58.3 % of patients treated with ECLS and in 25.0 % of the control patients [6].

CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, the current systemic review all available evidence on the effectiveness of ECLS in the continuous field of cardiac failure to cardiac arrest. In this review showed increased survival and favorable neurological outcomes in the ECLS-treated patients. Extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation can improve neurologic outcome after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest of cardiac origin; furthermore, pupil diameter on hospital arrival may be a key predictor to identify extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation candidates

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